

Scenario Analysis of Ecuador's Energy-Land-Water System using a CLEWs Model: Renewable Energy Expansion and Hydropower Supply Risk

Miguel Angel, Ministry of Environment and Energy, Ecuador
May 22, 2026

Keywords

CLEWs; OSeMOSYS; MUIO; Ecuador; energy transition; solar energy; wind energy; hydropower risk; Coca Codo Sinclair; regressive erosion; energy security; water–energy–land nexus.

Acknowledgements

This report was prepared as a result of the capacity-building process and technical collaboration developed during the CLEWs modeling course. I am grateful for the guidance, materials, and practical exercises provided throughout the training, which supported the development of a national-scale model integrating energy, land, water, and intersectoral linkages.

I also thank Climate Compatible Growth and Escuela Politécnica Nacional for their work as organizers of this EMP-LAC 2026.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

This report presents an exploratory scenario analysis of Ecuador's electricity system using a CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems) model implemented through MUIO and OSeMOSYS. A baseline model for 2020–2055 was developed through energy, land, water and interlinkage modules, and then compared with two scenarios. Scenario 1 tests increased deployment of non-conventional renewable energy, especially solar and wind power. Scenario 2 tests the sudden reduction of large-scale hydropower availability associated with the potential loss of Coca Codo Sinclair due to regressive erosion risk.

The results show that renewable expansion reduces dependence on large-scale hydropower and lowers emissions relative to the baseline; however, the corrected emissions profile indicates that residual emissions remain relevant due to natural gas and biofuel use, particularly in the later years of the model horizon. By contrast, the hydropower shock scenario generates a strong substitution toward fuel oil, natural gas and biofuel technologies, causing a major increase in emissions after 2030. The main recommendation is to combine accelerated renewable deployment with resilience planning for strategic hydropower infrastructure, grid flexibility, storage and risk-informed contingency planning.

1. Introduction

Ecuador's electricity system has historically relied strongly on hydropower, which provides low-carbon electricity but also creates exposure to hydrological variability and infrastructure-related risks. This dependence has become more relevant in recent years because drought, operational constraints and geomorphological processes in the Coca River basin have highlighted the need for a more resilient and diversified generation matrix. At the same time, national planning and policy discussions increasingly recognize the role of non-conventional renewable energy sources (NCRE), particularly solar photovoltaic and wind power, as complementary resources for system diversification.

The purpose of this report is to use a CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems) modelling framework to assess how Ecuador's electricity system could respond to two contrasting planning conditions. The first is an expansion of solar and wind generation, aligned with renewable energy policy signals and project pipelines. The second is a stress-test scenario in which the Coca Codo Sinclair hydropower plant, the country's largest hydroelectric asset, becomes unavailable due to risk at its intake infrastructure. The report focuses on the implications for the generation mix, fossil-fuel use and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions.

2. Methodology

The modelling exercise was developed using the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems) framework through MUIO, the user interface applied for OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System). The modelling horizon covers 2020–2055, with 2020–2023 treated as the historical calibration period and the following years represented as the optimization period. The energy module was developed first, using electricity generation technologies, transmission representation, demand profiles, techno-economic parameters, residual capacity and calibration constraints. The model structure follows a horizontal construction logic, where each technology chain is built and tested before adding further system components.

The land module introduced national land availability, selected crop categories, biofuel-related crops and non-agricultural land uses. The water module represented precipitation, irrigation water, public water demand, surface water and groundwater resources. The interlinkage module connected the systems by representing cooling-water requirements for thermal generation, electricity needs for water pumping, diesel use in agriculture and land requirements for biofuel production. This structure allows the model to represent cross-sector feedbacks, although the results remain exploratory and should not be interpreted as operational dispatch forecasts.

After the baseline was completed, two scenarios were prepared. Scenario 1, Renewable Energy Expansion, modifies the energy system to allow greater participation of solar and wind technologies, reflecting Ecuador’s policy and planning instruments for non conventional renewable energies (NCRE) deployment. Scenario 2, Hydropower Supply Risk, represents the loss of large-scale hydropower availability equivalent to the withdrawal of Coca Codo Sinclair from the system. Because the model aggregates hydropower technologies, this shock was represented as a reduction in the activity.

3. Results

The results show two clearly differentiated system responses. In the baseline, large-scale hydropower remains the dominant generation source throughout the modelling horizon. Biomass, medium-scale hydropower, natural gas, solar and wind complement the system, while fuel oil declines after the historical calibration period. This reflects the model’s preference for lower-cost or constrained low-carbon technologies once demand increases over time.

In Scenario 1, the expansion of solar and wind modifies the structure of the power mix. Large-scale hydropower continues to be important, but its relative participation decreases compared with the baseline. Wind generation expands progressively and becomes a visible contributor by the 2040s and 2050s, while solar generation also increases, although at a more moderate level. Fuel oil use declines and remains marginal in the long term. This result suggests that increasing NCRE availability can reduce the pressure placed on hydropower expansion and can create a more diversified electricity matrix.

Trata de poner % de cuánto se reduce hidro y aumentan los otros entre escenarios

Figure 1. Baseline and Scenario 1 generation/activity by technology: Renewable Energy Expansion.

The emissions graph for Scenario 1 shows that carbon dioxide emissions are lower than in the baseline during most of the optimization period, but the reduction is not a continuous movement toward near-zero emissions. After the historical calibration years, light fuel oil emissions decline significantly, which explains an important part of the improvement observed in the scenario. However, biofuel becomes a visible source of emissions in the medium and long term, while natural gas also remains present throughout the horizon. Therefore, Scenario 1 should be interpreted as a partial mitigation and diversification pathway. It reduces dependence on fuel oil and supports a lower-emissions trajectory compared with the baseline, but it does not fully decarbonize the power system because residual emissions from biofuel and natural gas remain relevant.

The comparison between the baseline and Scenario 1 shows that Emissions remain identical to the baseline between 2020 and 2030, but from 2031 onward Scenario 1 shows a progressive reduction. Over the full modelling horizon, cumulative emissions decrease from 229,352 t CO₂ in the baseline to 168,063 t CO₂ in Scenario 1, representing a reduction of **26.72%**. When only the differentiated period 2031–2055 is considered, cumulative emissions decrease by 37.33%. The largest annual reductions occur between 2047 and 2050, when Scenario 1 emits approximately 53% to 59% less than the baseline.

Figure 2. Baseline and Scenario 1 emissions by fuel category.

Scenario 2 presents a much more disruptive result. When large-scale hydropower availability is reduced, the model compensates by increasing fuel oil, natural gas and later biomass generation. Large-scale hydropower falls sharply in the scenario period, and the system depends on thermal generation to maintain supply. This response is consistent with a stress-test: when a strategic hydropower asset is removed abruptly and renewable alternatives are not sufficiently expanded beforehand, the least-cost feasible solution relies heavily on available dispatchable alternatives.

Figure 3. Baseline and Scenario 2 generation/activity by technology: Hydropower Supply Risk.

The emissions impact of Scenario 2 is the most relevant finding. Compared with the baseline, emissions rise rapidly after the hydropower shock and continue increasing toward 2055. By the end of the period, emissions are several times higher than the baseline level shown in the same figure. This indicates that a sudden loss of Coca Codo Sinclair would not only create an energy security challenge, but could also reverse mitigation gains by forcing the system toward fossil-based generation. The result reinforces the need to treat hydropower infrastructure risk as a central component of long-term energy and climate planning.

The comparison between the baseline and Scenario 2 shows a substantial increase in emissions caused by the assumed loss of large-scale hydropower availability. Over the full modelling period, cumulative emissions increase from 229,352 t CO₂ in the baseline to 730,865 t CO₂ in Scenario 2, equivalent to a 218.67% increase. The increase becomes particularly significant after 2030, when the model relies more heavily on light fuel oil, biofuel and natural gas to compensate for the reduced hydropower supply. Between 2031 and 2055, cumulative emissions are 275.37% higher than in the baseline, while in the final period 2050–2055 the increase reaches 349.65%.

Figure 4. Baseline and Scenario 2 emissions by fuel category.

5. Discussion

The comparison between the two scenarios provides three central insights. First, renewable energy expansion is a diversification strategy, not only a mitigation strategy. Scenario 1 shows that solar and wind technologies can reduce the model's reliance on large-scale hydropower while also limiting the role of fuel oil in the long term. However, the corrected emissions profile shows that this transition does not eliminate emissions, because biofuel and natural gas remain relevant contributors in the scenario. This is important for Ecuador because hydropower remains exposed to rainfall variability, sediment dynamics and physical infrastructure risks, while alternative technologies also require careful assessment of their emissions implications. A system with higher solar and wind participation would not automatically solve all reliability or decarbonization challenges, but it would reduce dependence on a small number of large hydropower assets and improve diversification.

Second, the hydropower risk scenario shows that delayed diversification can have high environmental and energy-security costs. In Scenario 2, the loss of large-scale hydropower triggers a rapid increase in dispatchable substitutes. These substitutes are mainly fuel oil and natural gas in the first part of the shock period, followed by a strong increase in biomass toward the end of the horizon. The emissions result confirms that the system response is carbon intensive. This is a critical planning message: protecting Coca Codo Sinclair is necessary, but it should not be the only risk-management strategy. The electricity system also needs credible alternatives that can be deployed before a shock occurs.

Third, the results suggest that NCRE deployment, storage and grid flexibility should be analyzed together. Solar and wind generation are variable resources; therefore, their contribution to resilience depends on complementary investments in transmission, storage, flexible generation, demand-side management and operational planning. The present model does not represent all of these operational details, but the scenario results still show that allowing more renewable generation changes the long-term structure of the system. A more detailed future version of the model could incorporate battery storage, pumped storage, demand response or imports as additional flexibility options.

It is important to mention that the study has several limitations. The first is aggregation. Coca Codo Sinclair is not represented as an individual plant unless the hydropower category is disaggregated, so Scenario 2 approximates its loss through a reduction in large-scale hydropower availability. The second limitation is the simplified treatment of costs, capacity factors and renewable resource potential.

Despite these limitations, the modelling exercise is useful for policy analysis. It shows that renewable expansion can support diversification and reduce emissions relative to the baseline, although the corrected Scenario 1 emissions graph confirms that residual emissions from biofuel and natural gas remain relevant and should not be overlooked. At the same time, an unmanaged hydropower shock can increase dependence on dispatchable substitutes and raise emissions sharply. The results therefore support a combined policy package: accelerate solar and wind deployment; assess the real emissions performance and sustainability of biofuel pathways; strengthen hydropower risk monitoring and protective works; expand flexibility resources; update contingency plans for hydropower outages; and use scenario modelling as a recurring input for energy planning and climate policy coordination.

7. Conclusion

This report applied a CLEWs model to compare a baseline pathway for Ecuador with two exploratory scenarios: renewable energy expansion and hydropower supply risk. Scenario 1 demonstrates that increasing solar and wind deployment can diversify the electricity matrix and reduce emissions relative to the baseline, mainly by lowering the long-term role of fuel oil. However, the emissions results show that this pathway does not fully decarbonize the system, because biofuel and natural gas remain relevant sources of residual emissions. Scenario 2 demonstrates that the sudden loss of Coca Codo Sinclair would generate a severe substitution challenge, with higher use of fuel oil, natural gas and biomass and a major increase in emissions. The main lesson is that energy transition and resilience planning must be addressed together. Ecuador should continue protecting strategic hydropower infrastructure while accelerating non-conventional renewable energy, storage, grid flexibility and contingency planning. Future work should refine the model by representing individual hydropower plants, validating units and costs, and testing

additional scenarios with storage, demand management, climate-sensitive hydrology and alternative assumptions for biofuel emissions.

References

Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) (2024) *Ecuador: Support for the Energy Transition and Promotion of Investments in the Energy Sector II. Second Programmatic Policy-Based Loan*. Washington, D.C.: Inter-American Development Bank.

International Energy Agency (IEA) (2026) *Ecuador: Electricity*. Paris: International Energy Agency.

Ministry of Energy and Mines. (2024). *Plan Maestro de Electricidad 2023–2032* [Electricity Master Plan 2023–2032]. Government of Ecuador.

Ministry of Energy and Mines. (2024). *Capítulo 4: Plan de Expansión de Generación* [Chapter 4: Generation Expansion Plan]. In *Plan Maestro de Electricidad 2023–2032* [Electricity Master Plan 2023–2032]. Government of Ecuador.

